

Recommended citation: Virkki-Hatakka, T., Mielonen, K., IkÄrvalko, M., Eskelinen, H., & KerkkÄnen, K. (2020). Working-Lige-Integrated Curriculum Design and Enhancing Thesis Process. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1146-1158). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654207.

WORKING-LIFE-INTEGRATED ENGINEERING CURRICULUM DESIGN AND ENHANCING THESIS PROCESS

T. Virkki-Hatakka¹

D.Sc.(tech), Project manager
LUT School of Business and Management
Lappeenranta, Finland
E-mail: tvh@lut.fi

K. Mielonen

D.Sc. (tech), University Lecturer
LUT School of Energy Systems
Lappeenranta, Finland
E-mail: katriina.mielonen@lut.fi

M. Ikävalko

D.Sc. (Econ. & Bus. Adm.), Associate professor
LUT School of Business and Management
Lappeenranta, Finland
E-mail: markku.ikavalko@lut.fi

H. Eskelinen

D.Sc.(tech), Head of degree programmes in mechanical engineering
LUT School of Energy Systems
Lappeenranta, Finland
E-mail: harri.eskelinen@lut.fi

K. Kerkkänen

D.Sc.(tech), University Lecturer
LUT School of Energy Systems
Lappeenranta, Finland
E-mail: kimmo.kerkanen@lut.fi

Conference Key Areas: *HE & Business, Career support, Future engineering skills*

Keywords: *Engineering curriculum, Working-life integration, Thesis process, Future expertise*

ABSTRACT

Working life, and the expertise it requires, is undergoing a rapid change. For this reason, it is particularly important for universities to focus on future working life skills and competences needed in a variety of work roles and working environments. The

¹ Corresponding Author

T. Virkki-Hatakka

tvh@lut.fi

student's expertise in his / her field develops throughout the course of his / her studies. In both B.Sc. and M.Sc. thesis phase, a student should already be able to utilize and demonstrate the expertise to a certain extent.

This study presents a work-integrated curriculum model designed for engineering education. Within the identified drivers that guide the curriculum work in the technical fields, a model that considers the perspectives of corporate cooperation and business knowledge, was constructed and piloted. The model also provides a more flexible integration of future development trends into the education.

In order to make the thesis process more efficient, a virtual environment for the internship and thesis exchange was planned. It approaches the development of expertise in such a way that the university does not define the knowledge goals, but students are guided to do it themselves. This also includes interactivity: although the thesis always has certain limitations, it is not removed from its context and environment, but defines what is expected of the author. The platform has been piloted in the Mechanical Engineering bachelor's thesis process at the university, and the results will be discussed in this paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

The expertise needed in today's working life is different now than twenty years ago. Routine expertise, which works effectively in a familiar situation, is often no longer sufficient, but many tasks such as leadership, research, planning and combining these require adaptive and appropriate expertise. For this reason, it is particularly important that also universities as education providers will focus on the future skills, qualifications and competences in different jobs and environments.

The aspects of permanent needs to respond to the fast-changing demands of engineering education and to continuously develop its programs and improve curricula and teaching/learning arrangements have been highlighted especially in context of Bologna process for years. [1]. It has also been discussed how multi- and transdisciplinary teaching and research could possibly coexist in a meaningful way in today's university structures, and especially how these viewpoints could be integrated with sustainable development [2]. Some researches highlight needs and present recommendations for developing engineering education to increase students' "soft skills", e.g. personal achievement motivation, leadership potential, personal effectiveness and self-presentation [3]. Number of studies have also been done about entrepreneurship as one of the key expectations to engineers and their training. These efforts have been integrated e.g. with students' skills of business and society aspects. The effects on curricular design and academic reform have been discussed correspondingly [4].

After graduation, general working life skills such as teamwork, communication and problem solving expertise are essential in addition to the degree of substance expertise [5]. Both substance skills and general working life skills are part of the expertise required from graduates, which also includes some knowledge of companies

and practices in their own field. In a high level of expertise, theoretical, practical and experiential knowledge are strongly integrated, although in traditional teaching these have been treated separately [6].

The students' expertise in their field develops throughout studies, and in the final thesis they should already be able to apply and show expertise to a certain extent. Unfortunately nowadays, students are generally not well shaped by technological experience due to tightening graduation deadlines. In order to support the development of professional expertise besides substance education, it has to be taken into account already in curriculum development work. Also, it is important that students have a realistic understanding on their expertise, and what is expected of them in working life.

This article presents a model of curricula integrated into the world of work, and a related, guided thesis process which were implemented in a mechanical engineering degree programme. The guided thesis process was piloted in spring semester 2020, and the gained results from this pilot are also discussed here.

2 METHODS

2.1 Working-life integrated curriculum design

A curriculum refers to an action plan that guides education and learning, the development of which aims at high-quality student learning. From the student's point of view, the curriculum is either a study guide or a personal study plan, and for the teacher it provides an aid for locating and implementing his/her own teaching. At university level, curricula consist of educational programmes or comparable educational products, illustrating the expertise of the discipline and the relationship with other disciplines and society [7]. In addition, there are some political regulations of the national education system concerning curricula in education organisations [8].

When designing a model of curriculum work integrated into working life, drivers guiding curriculum work in the field of technology were identified in the first phase. These strongly contributing factors include several educational policy objectives, which are set both from outside and inside of the university. In addition, in educational products, such as master's programmes, there are requirements which are imposed both for the development of the content, and implementation of teaching methods. Development in discipline, as well as in companies and working life, set their own requirements in curriculum design, and some drivers may originate also in an individual level.

Universities are subject to external guidance, which will be influenced by the guidelines drawn by, e.g., the Ministry of Education and Culture. The time targets for graduation and the cost-effectiveness of teaching activities, profiling and possible regional policy solutions, are examples of these principles. Through the university's internal guidance, curriculum work is guided by various strategies, such as concern strategy, internationalisation and digital strategy and the strategy of an entrepreneurial university. One of the drivers from within the university, is the educational-product thinking, which builds study modules for different target groups, such as international

master's programmes or education programmes for life-long learning. The design and development of teaching content also depends on, for example, identified or predicted future trends, the emphasis on multidisciplinary and the skills required of graduate students. When choosing a method of education implementation, at least the following factors have to be taken into account: available financial, time and labour resources, possible business cooperation, target groups for education and flexibility.

The forces driving the design of educational products are shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Drivers for the content and development of educational products.

Based on Fig. 1, it was possible to build and pilot a curriculum work model that takes into account the perspectives originating from business cooperation and the skill needs of companies more clearly and faster than before. The model summarises the curriculum process by increasing the teaching of research-based work before starting the thesis and, on the other hand, preparing a working-life oriented way together with the thesis sponsor [9]. The model consists of basic studies in research methodology, laboratory work course in the corporate environment, and subsequent thesis. The implementations are not separate courses, but support the thesis, as shown in Fig. 2.

The main part of the curriculum work is the laboratory work course, the scope of which is 2-30 credits, depending on the company-oriented project. This flexibility makes it possible to use the course in both bachelor's and master's stages. The course develops student's capacity to use research approach and solve the real problems identified by the companies. At the same time, it provides the basis for longer-term business cooperation and allows the preparation and start of the thesis. The course will be carried out as a project that is planned together with the company, the student and the supervisor from the university. A project plan, follow-up reports and a final report are prepared for the project, reflecting the implementation of the plan.

Fig. 2. As part of the curriculum work process that is integrated into working life, the thesis implementation model is used to support the advancement of both international and domestic students. The core of the process lies on three integrated courses.

When analyzing the effects of content and development drivers (Fig.1) on the implementation model (Fig.2), the most strongly influencing driver in practical development work has been the flexible digital implementation of course modules due to the modern requirements of distance learning possibilities. However, from the content point of view, the profiling based on the university's own strategic strengths is the most important factor. Nowadays, the course materials are developed for international students and the most used language is English. Behind these almost self-evident aspects there are number of connections between the drivers and the model. Firstly, the content of research methods course module is required to give basis for the scientific approaches needed in the *Laboratory work course* and further during the thesis project. The content should be discussed personally with each student and with the company in which the exercise work will be completed. Secondly, it is important to notice that the total amount of credits of the *Laboratory work course* can be established to be between 2-30 credits which gives students some freedom to select either only this course module in its entire broadness or keep the amount of credits a bit limited and select e.g. some business-oriented studies instead. This flexibility of credits makes it possible to take into account the driving forces of business cooperation, regional policy and entrepreneurship. These aspect are to ensure

students' better employment capabilities at the specific company in which he/she has worked during his/her laboratory work course already before the final thesis will be completed. Thirdly, during the *Laboratory work course* it is also possible to give the company the possibility to get familiar with university's expertise (profile) and take advantage from university's knowledge before the thesis project. Both sides can learn from each other and the co-operation between the student, the company and the university has a longer perspective.

2.2 Improving the efficiency of the thesis process

At the end of the studies, it is important to support the smooth running of the thesis process. To this end, the evaluation criteria for a thesis in working life cooperation were clarified and the Stock market of internship and master thesis positions, aimed at improving the thesis process, was built and piloted. Stock market here refers to a platform where students and organizations may find each other, i.e., it does not mean an ongoing trading of these positions.

One of the aspects increasing the novelty value of the process is the way to increase the time period in which the student, the company and the university follow the common path of studies. It is also important to notice that even though the company and the university are involved more to the process, the individual choice of the research topic and thesis topic are still offered to the student himself/herself. Of course, the strategic goals of the university and the values set by the company are building the framework for student's choice but to keep students motivated some freedom is left to them.

It has been shown that different computer and distance learning assisted ways, e.g. MOOC [10] or augmented reality applications [11], can increase students' motivation. Together with them the given freedom to students can give promising results in learning. Our model is supported with the driving force of digitalization, which means in this case, that we apply Moodle environment in each of the courses included to our model. There is evidence available that this kind of assisted freedom of choice really supports students' motivation [12].

It is also noticeable that scientific aspects are combined with practical aspects together with company and university sides. In many cases, these aspects are regarded as separate ones, thus the importance of integration is known in many universities around the world. One minor thing is that in this model, it is possible to tune the amount of obligatory engineering studies if needed.

2.2.1 Evaluation of the thesis in working life cooperation

The thesis in the field of technology usually involves a student, a university supervisor and a company that offers the subject of the work. Often, a company representative is also acting as a second supervisor of the work. The company evaluates the student's skills and expertise with its own criteria, which often include 21st century skills, such

as sensemaking, social intelligence, applied mindset, and the ability to operate in a multidisciplinary and multicultural environment.

The University, on the other hand, uses other criteria for evaluating the thesis, which make it difficult to directly assess the expertise. The students' own perceptions of their skills and the development of expertise are reflected in e.g. some questionnaires by a trade union, which offer different options for expressing competence. These above-mentioned criteria are all different.

In these projects involving both the student, the company and the university, it is crucial that all parties agree what kind of outcome is sought. Otherwise, one of the possible stumbling blocks may be if practicality and research are seen differently in the university and company. It can also be difficult for students to understand the difference between a practical problem and research questions. Unfortunately, quite often the research issues in students' final theses are addressed by a practical problem, and for example, a question beginning with '*Why*' may be not presented and answered. This usually means that the applicability of the results is limited only to applications analogous to the situation studied.

In a working-life oriented thesis, it is also important to define already at the beginning how to work together [13]. A starting meeting can be held between the student, the supervisor and the company, so that they can agree on guidance, schedule, possible costs and inventions, objectives and evaluation of the finished work. A common evaluation rubric which is tailored at the beginning to suit the specific work, can be a great help in evaluating the thesis. A good thesis produces new information for both the company and the scientific community through the identified research methods.

2.2.2. Stock market of internship and final thesis positions

In order to improve the efficiency of the thesis process, the development of expertise is approached on the *Internship and thesis stock market* planned for mechanical engineering degree programme. Here, the university does not define competence objectives, but the students are directed to do it themselves by familiarising with their target company and subcontracting networks, and by identifying what skills are needed in this workplace. This also includes interactivity: although the thesis always includes certain boundaries, it is not removed from its environment, but can be used to determine what is expected of the author. It is important that students are able to show their own activity in forming the required contacts with companies and possible supervisors, see Fig.3.

Figure 3. The role of student's own activity in finding the internship and final thesis position.

Today, there is an increasing effort to ensure that studies are time-independent and independent of education. Accordingly, the development environment for theses was also built on an online platform.

Traditionally, both the student's and the supervisor's knowledge background is reflected in the thesis. In addition, when a representative from a company is also taken into account, the required expertise will be raised even more. At best, when these different types of expertise meet, high-quality and creative solutions are achieved. According to Talikka [14], it is easier to handle expert interfaces in an objective environment where information encounter, and it is not so much individuals. Thus, the development environment for theses may serve as an excellent meeting place for these different expertise.

The Moodle implementation of the stock market was built on the schedule frame shown in Fig. 4, which is applicable to the control of both bachelor's and master's thesis. In B.Sc. thesis, the time from beginning to end is 4 months, and in M.Sc. thesis 6 months. The implementation consists of 6 different sections: *Abstract and introduction, Literature review, Research methods, Result, Discussion and Summary*, which all include pertinent lectures and exercises. In the schedule, the description of the research problem, the method description and the reflection section receive especially much guidance since before, they have been found to be difficult for students to internalise. In addition to lessons and learning tasks, the implementation schedule includes several hours of individual student guidance and on the other hand, presentation of the progress of the work to other students. These check points are marked with an 'x' in Fig. 4. This way, students' theses, and their methodical choices can benefit collectively the entire group of participants. All supervisors who had their students in the process were also kept informed of the ongoing thesis topics and their progress.

Fig. 4. The schedule frame created as the basis for the supervision of the thesis.

When students understand their future operating environment, the desired expertise is created. The most important expertise that is needed for the work is the deep understanding of substance, although general capabilities are also important. *The Stock market of internship and final thesis positions* site can guide students in this. In the *Subcontracting Networks* section, students are instructed to ask questions about expertise and find answers to them. The students can also get help in making a job application from the thesis exchange, which often asks you to describe their skills. These cannot be pre-given, but the student must find and dictate them himself.

The virtual implementation of the internship and thesis exchange takes into account the international nature of the students: the site is made in four languages: Finnish, English, Russian and French. In this way, international thesis workers are offered the opportunity to practice their skills and to become better equipped in Finnish working life.

The guided thesis process is of paramount importance in the bachelor's phase, but also useful in the master's degree, especially in the field of research methodology and project work skills. The department of mechanical engineering has tested three different ways of completing the studies on the *Basics of research methodology* (4 cr): either entirely as distance studies, traditional literature or intensive courses. Out of these, intensive course has proven to be the most effective. The guided thesis process also includes a specified guidance on information retrieval of the thesis, which is held by the information specialists of the Science Library. In addition, information retrieval workshops are carried out as part of the guidance of bachelor's work. The material is also suitable for distance learning.

3 RESULTS

The curriculum model together with the scheduled, guided thesis process has been piloted in the university with mechanical engineering students working on their B.Sc. thesis during spring semester 2020. The results from the pilot showed that the new model has been quite effective. About 60% of students who started their thesis in

January were able to complete it until May. It is also expected that about 20% more of them will complete their work until the end of July since supervisors were able to contact 80% of candidates during the last weeks of semester. Only some students dropped out from the course. The final number of participating students was 40. Table 1 summarises the main findings and future progressions in the curriculum work model.

Table 1. Experiences from piloting the curriculum model in the academic year 2019-2020.

Curriculum work model integrated into working life, pilot 2019-2020		
Tool	Findings	Next steps
Exploitation of content and development drivers of educational products	The most strongly influencing driver is the educational product. The <i>flexible digital implementation</i> is highlighted. In content, the <i>profiling</i> based on the university's own strategic strengths is the most important factor.	Increasing business cooperation by taking advantage of the marketing opportunities created by different educational products.
Utilising the combination of research methodology, laboratory work course and thesis	From the point of view of business cooperation, the laboratory course has proven to be particularly successful.	Improve the implementation by grouping, based on selected project work topics.
Utilizing the Stock market of internship and master thesis positions	45 students enrolled in the pilot course in Moodle environment. However, all possibilities in the environment have not been utilized at all.	Integration of the Moodle environment into a research methodology course or other professional subject in the next curriculum work round.
Take advantage of a scheduled guided thesis process	42 students started in the pilot phase, (target to be completed May-June/2020).	Highlighting that the Moodle package will be implemented twice during an academic year. About 1/3 of those who were now enrolled had come too early.

A clear majority of students who gave feedback (n=20) about the guided thesis process pilot, were satisfied with the amount and content of both lectures and learning tasks. Supervisor meetings that were part of the process, received particular praise. Up to 90% of respondents thought the number of teacher meetings was appropriate, and the remaining 10% would have liked even more of them. All respondents told that the meetings helped to make a lot of progress on B.Sc. thesis work. A guidance organised by the library was also found useful by 95% of respondents. A technical implementation of the course site was also considered good by 85% of respondents. A few critical comments were given about the course schedule in relation to bachelor's work. Also, different kind of B.Sc. theses could have been better taken into account; some of them are more theoretical and some include more empirical work for example

in laboratories. Fig. 5. shows that students wanted to add writing workshops and meetings with supervisors in the process. Lecture videos were also mentioned besides lectures, which might reflect the influence of COVID-19 pandemic during spring 2020.

Fig. 5. Feedback: what students said they want to add in the guided thesis process.

In general, students believed that the guided thesis process contributed to the completion of the work, and most of them thought that the impact was high.

Teachers' feedback was also positive. Especially, supervisors felt that they can concentrate better on the substance in the meetings, since they do not have to go through e.g. the IMRAD structure separately with every student. They also said that the students are now much more active in the meetings. The overall progress of bachelor workers seems to be more even, too:

"A few students had difficulties in achieving/following the bachelor's course schedules for the results. In any case, few slower ones would have stretched over the summer in previous years, but now they are also trying to finish the work in this spring. It's a very good improvement over previous years."

- A supervisor

Based on supervisors' feedback, it also appears that, besides the formulation of the report, the new model gives students more thought about the role of research questions, ensuring the reliability of the results and other issues relevant to the scientific level of the thesis.

The results of this study seem to imply that, even though uncovering the curriculum design to the outside expectations increases the number of potential variations in the flow of studies, the process pays off in form of increased study motivation and outcome regarding especially the demands of thesis and modern work life. Additionally, it seems that this approach is an iterative process, for years to come. Challenging yes, but it may also provide a new insight into the quality of universities' educational processes. The shared path between a university, an industrial partner and a student

begins from the bachelor level studies providing a strong impulse and solid foundation for the last standing and productive co-operation in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] Heitmann, G. (2005). Challenges of engineering education and curriculum development in the context of the Bologna process, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 30:4, 447-458, DOI: 10.1080/03043790500213136
- [2] Ashford, N.A. (2004). Major challenges to engineering education for sustainable development: What has to change to make it creative, effective, and acceptable to the established disciplines?, *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, Vol. 5 No. 3, pp. 239-250. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14676370410546394>
- [3] Aleksandrov, A.Y., Zakharova, A.N., Nikolaev, E. L. (2015). New challenges in engineering education: Personal advancement for better marketability of future professionals, *International Conference on Interactive Collaborative Learning (ICL)*, Florence, 2015, pp. 452-454, doi: 10.1109/ICL.2015.7318072.
- [4]. Jørgensen, U., & Pineda, A. F. V. (2012). Entrepreneurship and response strategies to challenges in engineering and design education. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 28(2), 407-415.
- [5] Crebert, G., Bates, M., Bell, B., Patrick, C-J. & Cragolini, V. (2004). Developing generic skills at university, during work placement and in employment: graduates' perceptions. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 23(2), 147–165.
- [6] Tynjälä, P. (2007). Integratiivinen pedagogiikka osaamisen kehittämisessä. In a book H. Kotila, A. Mutanen & M V Volanen (eds.) *Taidon tieto*. Helsinki. Edita, 11-36, *In Finnish*
- [7] Gunnarson, S. (2010) Outlook. In: Crawley, E., Malmqvist, J., Ostlund, S., Brodeur, D. (Eds.), *Rethinking Engineering Education: the CDIO Approach*. Springer, New York, USA, 241-256.
- [8] Karjalainen, A. (ed.) (2007). Akateeminen opetussuunnitelmatyö. Oulun Yliopisto, opetuksen kehittämissyksikkö. Available at: http://www.oamk.fi/c5/files/1015/5429/2794/akateeminen_opetussuunnitelmatyo_2007.pdf, *In Finnish*
- [9] Levander, I., M., Mikkola, M. (2009) Core curriculum analysis; a tool for educational design. *J. Arg. Edu. Ext.* 15, 275-286.
- [10].Borras-Gene, O., Martinez-Nunez, M., Fidalgo-Blanco, A. (2016). New Challenges for the Motivation and Learning in Engineering Education Using Gamification in MOOC, *International Journal of Engineering Education* Vol. 32, No. 1(B), pp. 501–512
- [11].Gutiérrez, J.M., Meneses Fernández, M.D., (2014). Applying augmented reality in engineering education to improve academic performance & student motivation, *The International journal of engineering education*, Vol. 30, no.3, 2014, pp. 625-635

- [12].Radenski, A.A. (2009). Freedom of choice as motivational factor for active learning, ACM SIGCSE Bulletin July 2009, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1595496.1562891>
- [13] Vihervaara, T. (2015). Yritysyhteistyö opetuksessa, käytännön käsikirja yliopistoille ja yrityksille, Aalto-yliopisto, Nordprint, Helsinki, *In Finnish*
- [14] Talikka, M. (2018). Recognizing required changes to higher education engineering programs' information literacy education as a consequence of research problems becoming more complex, PhD thesis, LUT university, School of Energy Systems, Mechanical engineering. Available at: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-335-238-4>